

THE IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON CONSUMERS BEHAVIOR AND E-COMMERCE GROWTH IN SERBIA

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Abstract: *Global e-commerce market is growing from year to year, although in most countries it is a very low share of total sales. Online shopping in Serbia is growing slowly, but data show that Serbian customers are spending more and more time using online applications and social networks. Online shopping has risen in value by 28% in 2021 compared to the year 2020. On the other hand shopping in stores, recorded a value increase of only 3.1%. The COVID-19 pandemic has changed consumers' habits and behavior, as well as the organization and business of companies in Serbia. E-commerce in Serbia has doubled in 2020 as a result of lockdown, compared to the year before the COVID-19 pandemic.*

The paper presents data on accelerated development of e-commerce as an activity that facilitates Serbian trade. The aim is to highlight the role that e-commerce has in changing consumer behavior during the crisis.

INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 crisis led to slowdown in global economic activity, and to an increase in e-commerce and acceleration of digital transformation. The digital economy and e-commerce bring new opportunities and new challenges to achieving the goals of sustainable development. With the introduction of lockdown measures and quarantines, businesses and consumers have become increasingly digital providing and buying more goods and services online. It is estimated that its share in global retail trade increased from 10.4 percent in 2017 to 14.1 percent in 2019, while the share of e-commerce in global retail increased from 14% in 2019 to about 17% in 2020 (UNCTAD, 2021).

E-commerce has great potential for diversifying the scale and geographical range of trade opportunities for developing countries and expanding the scope of both existing companies and new businesses. It also plays an increasingly important role in the supply and distribution of goods and services in domestic markets (Dutta & Lanvin, 2020). E-commerce growth, however, has slowed in many developing countries with barriers to infrastructure, finance, resources and governance. Countries that overcome these barriers and establish frameworks to enable the development of e-commerce will be better placed to reap its potential benefits and responses to challenges, both domestically and internationally, while those that do not risk become less dynamic in national borders and less competitive abroad (WEF, 2020). The effects of the pandemic on the use of digital technologies, especially the capacity of the e-commerce sector to supply, in developing countries and least developed countries, will depend on the capacity of reforms sustainability and investment. They should be aimed at building the preparedness of overall national e-commerce ecosystems, and fostering sustainable growth in the long run.

The global pandemic has fully strengthened the need for e-commerce. Instead of limited offline shopping of one of the many options that consumers had, e-commerce has become the primary way to buy. The COVID-19 pandemic has changed online shopping behavior in long turn. With all non-essential product stores closing around the world for most of 2020, and increasing social distancing, online shopping has become the norm and e-commerce sales begin to grow significantly. However, this has affected e-commerce around the world differently. Consumers of different nationalities, genders, age groups and purchasing power spent and purchased differently during the pandemic, and some industries were more willing to expand their digital offering than others.

GROWTH OF E-COMMERCE IN SERBIA DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC

Modern retail is becoming a global industry. An indicator of this assertion is expansion of domestic chains and networks to foreign markets especially present in e-commerce, given the fact that online sales know no geographical boundaries, and goods / services can be placed on both domestic and foreign markets, as stated in Program for the development of electronic commerce in the Republic of Serbia for the period 2019-2020. E-commerce as a form of purchasing goods and services is growing in popularity among the citizens of the Republic of Serbia, as the number of Internet users in the Republic of Serbia increases. Possession of computers and smartphones became mandatory, and the former obstacles to their use, both financial and technical, have almost disappeared. According to a Statistical Office of Republic of Serbia 2018 study, more than 1,800,000 people bought something online.

The global health crisis caused by COVID-19 pandemic has changed consumers' habits and behavior, as well as the organization and business of companies in Serbia. According to research by the Serbian Chamber of Commerce (SCC), e-commerce in Serbia has doubled in 2020 as a result of lockdown, compared to the year before the COVID-19 pandemic. In March and April 2020, the first two months of pandemic outbreak, in addition to basic groceries, computers and computer equipment, small household appliances, clothes and shoes were mostly bought online. The SCC analysis indicates that online food sales increased tenfold in that period compared to the average monthly turnover before the pandemic. Large retail chains have activated and strengthened their online stores and their own delivery services due to the required high standards for the transport of food products. Technical goods retailers have significantly offset the decline in traditional sales and losses due to closed shops and malls, mostly thanks to large purchases of computers that companies bought to equip employees to work from home. Small retailers and production companies reacted quickly and took the opportunity to access free of charge or minimal fee platforms specially created for them by IT companies specializing in e-commerce. Online platforms that have transformed businesses from traditional sales channels to online stores have seen three-digit growth in users. Mostly food products were bought, and the average consumer basket in online sales consisted of 56 items. Catering facilities, particularly affected by the pandemic crisis, have also adapted to the crisis by introducing food delivery in order to retain workers and allow customers to use their services unhindered. According to SCC data, these companies had a large increase in the number of orders, in April as much as 109 percent more than in March 2020.

E-commerce is an indicator of business sophistication and a way to enter a new market. A revolution in e-commerce and a major change in the perception of the importance of online shopping were brought in 2020. However, e-commerce in the Republic of Serbia is still relatively underdeveloped and the benefits offered by this way of doing business are rarely used, although the market is constantly growing. According to the USAID 2020 Survey, many companies in the Republic of Serbia emphasize the importance of e-commerce: 71% of companies agree that the importance of e-commerce as a business channel will show great global growth in the period to come, and 58% believe that the same thing happens when it comes to the Republic of Serbia. Of the 1,000 companies surveyed, 66% have their own website, but only 12% have an online store, and even fewer offer online payment options (8%). The USAID research has shown that companies that have a website and / or e-shop sell more outside the cities in which they have their headquarters, and companies with a website had revenue growth of 41%, and with online shop have growth of 31%. This is especially evident in small companies that have the online payment option and which had 33 percent larger revenues than similar companies that do not have this service. The absolute majority, as many as 82 percent of respondents rate online sales as equal, or even more important sales channel than the traditional sales model.(USAID, 2020)

The companies most affected by the crisis, which recorded a drop in revenue of over 70 percent, have seen the greatest importance of e-commerce, both globally - 92%, and in Serbia - 80%.

The year 2020 also brought growth in online payments. Among the respondents who have online sales, there was a significant increase in the share of companies that have implemented the online payment option.

The Serbian Business Register Agency (SBRA) records show an increase in the number of companies that registered retail trade by mail or via the Internet as their predominant activity, especially after the beginning of the pandemic. In 2020, 169 companies and 276 entrepreneurs who registered retail trade by mail or online were established, while in first two months of 2021, 20 companies and 56 entrepreneurs registered the same type of business. For comparison, in 2019, 114 companies and 255 entrepreneurs were registered for sale by mail or online, and in 2018, only 10 companies and 16 entrepreneurs were registered.

Not only businesses became digitally transformed, but so have the habits and needs of customers, who have become more open to shopping through

digital channels. Internet retailers hope that the habits of customers will remain, as well as that the way of thinking of customers regarding e-commerce in Serbia will change permanently.

According to the data of the National Bank of Serbia, the number of Serbian dinar (RSD) transactions paid online by card doubled in 2020 compared to 2019, that is, 14.2 million transactions were paid with cards when it comes to domestic purchases. The value of goods and services paid online by card in domestic currency in 2020 has doubled - to a total of 32.2 billion RSD. When spending in euros, dollars, pounds and Swiss francs is added to that, we come to the amount of about 455 million euros that the citizens of Serbia spent in 2020 paying with cards for online purchases.

During 2020, there were 39 million more payment card transactions compared to 2019, and 93 billion dinars were spent more than in the year before the pandemic, according to data from the National Bank of Serbia on the number and value of payment transactions made by cards and electronic money, whether it's withdrawing money from an ATM, paying at a point of sale, or shopping online.

The number of internet transactions paid by card in RSD recorded a growth by 103.55% in 2020 compared to 2019, and 59.58% in 2021 compared to 2020.

Also, the value of transactions in RSD increased by 81.27 percent in 2020 compared to the previous year and by 72.03% in 2021 compared to 2020. Due to a significant increase in the number of online transactions, the total value of realized transactions paid by card online in 2020 compared to 2019 has a jump of 33.37%. Total value of online card transactions in 2021 was 797 million euros, which is 75.77% more than in 2020.

On the other hand, it is noticed that the average value of the order decreases during the observed period. The average value of a transaction made via the Internet in the RSD during 2020 is 2,271.85 dinars, or 36.63 EUR. The decline in the average value was expected especially due to the fact that the number of new customers on the Internet increased in 2020, and in practice it has been shown that new customers make their first purchases in smaller amounts. Increasing the average value of an order is one of the many goals of every online retailer, and this value increased in 2021 to 2,449,18 RSD or 48.22 EUR.

The frequency of purchases has changed compared to 2020, and given the fact that online market in Serbia received a large number of new customers

in 2021, who had not bought online until then, this is the expected result. Also, spending in domestic online stores in 2021 participated with 59.17%, in regard to consumption in foreign online stores.

Table 1. The number of transactions paid with cards in domestic currency (RSD) exceeds the value of transactions paid with cards in other currencies collectively

	<i>2019</i>	<i>2020</i>	<i>2021</i>
1. Number of online transactions of purchase of goods and services paid by cards in foreign currencies	5.2 million	6 million	8,2 million
2. Number of online transactions of purchase of goods and services paid by cards in EUR	2.9 million	3.2 million	4,4 million
3. Number of online transactions of purchase of goods and services paid by cards in USD	2.1 million	2.6 million	3.6 million
4. Number of online transactions of purchase of goods and services paid by cards in other foreign currencies	137,000	162,000	173,000
5. Number of online transactions of purchase of goods and services paid by cards in RSD	6.9 million	14.1 million	22,6 million

More than usual, consumers bought clothes online during the pandemic, but above all food, which at some point recorded a growth of more than 200 percent, while sales of clothing and footwear grew by 100 percent, technical devices by 50 percent. Thus, the income from e-commerce in Serbia in 2020 year was 395 million euros, and there were as many as 3.3 million buyers on the Internet.

Depending on the level of development of digital business, the growth of existing retailers last year ranged between 200 and 400 percent. There are also a large number of newly opened online stores. More serious sales

growth required more serious preparation. Companies that had developed processes, a good web shop and an efficient team managed to skip several years of organic growth. E-commerce mostly sells appliances, clothes, shoes and books. During the lockdown, the sale of home exercise equipment, supplementation and food came to the fore.

According to a Statistical Office of Republic of Serbia data, the largest number of customers on the Internet in 2020 bought clothes and sports products (52%) and sports equipment (26%), a 20% home appliances, slightly smaller percent computers and other electronic equipment, but also furniture and toys. More than eight percent of online shoppers ordered food from restaurants, which is why delivery companies could boast of a hard but successful year. This trend has continued throughout 2021, and the largest number of customers in Serbia bought clothes online (46%), sports products and equipment (45%), home appliances (28%), and electronic equipment (24%).

A large number of companies from certain industries could not adapt to e-commerce. The reason is the type of activity they are engaged in. The hotel industry and tourism in general, air traffic, but also the entire event industry (event organization) has suffered huge losses. The 2020 has been challenging for all other activities as well. Companies that could do business, as long as they invested in digitalization and the (internet) sales sector in a timely manner, could quickly (re)organize and activate their online sales. On the other hand, companies that were already active in online sales had the opportunity to test their capabilities in the true sense of the word, given that internet communication and sales became the primary form of trade, immediately after the pandemic was declared in mid-March of 2020.

Although e-commerce in Serbia achieved very high annual turnover growth rates in the last two years, Serbia lagged behind developed countries due to the low base. Compared to countries in the region, and especially the most developed European countries, internet users in Serbia shopped the least online, in quantity and in value. The average internet user in Serbia spent 20 percent less than in Albania in 2019, ten times less than in Austria, and even 15 times behind users in Great Britain, which have the most developed e-commerce market, according to Statista.

Online trade in the European Union is also experiencing significant growth. Nine of ten residents in the Netherlands, Denmark or Great Britain shopped online last year. More than 80 percent of citizens in Germany, Sweden, and Ireland shopped online, while the countries with the fewest online shoppers in EU are Bulgaria (42 percent), Romania (45 percent) and Italy (49 percent).

Among the countries in the region, Romania has also recorded the highest growth in past two years - as much as 27 percent, and this type of purchase is also growing in Croatia and Hungary, according Statista.

According to Eurostat data, as many as 64 percent of buyers in the EU has opt for purchasing wardrobe and footwear during COVID-19 pandemic. In second place are movies and series, which were purchased online by 32 percent of buyers. Deliveries from restaurants and catering are in third place with 29 percent of buyers, then the purchase of furniture, cosmetic products, books and magazines, computers and mobile phones, and music.

CONCLUSION

The period of strict stay in homes measures and restriction of movement due to quarantine during the COVID-19 pandemic, showed the full potential of e-commerce in Serbia. The pandemic has undoubtedly changed consumer habits, so many customers have used e-commerce services for the first time, and others have only strengthen this pattern of behavior. Therefore, the assumption is that e-commerce will still prosper, and the pandemic will only determine its reach.

The pandemic has accelerated the spread of e-commerce, and many companies in Serbia have realized the potential and even the need to reach customers and clients by doing business online. More than 80 percent of companies that have sales on the internet believe that their online business is equally or more important than their traditional business and retail sales. However, the use of e-commerce in Serbia is still at an early stage of development and adoption, and e-commerce structures have not been able to provide infrastructure ready for use in response to COVID-19. In Serbia, a smaller segment of the economy has adjusted its business to the crisis through digitalization and e-commerce, but there has been an increase in interest in doing so.

Perhaps the best tool that Serbia could use to strengthen its economic growth and join global chains is the digitalization of the economy. Serbia has great potential in this area, with a strong talent base and state support, which are factors in the rapid adaptation to the global digital revolution.

In 2022 there are about four million consumers in Serbia who shop online, which represents a great potential for the development of this type of shopping. E-commerce in Serbia kept growing in 2022, and it is expected that by the end of the year ratio of online and traditional shopping to become 50/50. It is much more important to maintain this trend of rapid growth of e-

commerce in the years to come. Expectations are that by 2024, online customers to grow by more than 20 percent in Serbia. However, although the quality of service in e-commerce business is getting better and customers are strengthening their trust in this way of shopping, there is still plenty of room for further development and growth. Serbian marketers have realized the importance of the digital economy and necessity of digital transformation. This led to the improvement of the quality of services, better delivery, expansion and offer, and long term planning in order to use this sales channel equally. The customers recognized these efforts, began to gain trust and to purchase more, and return as online buyers. In last two years, improvement is evident, but continuous education of both buyers and sellers is still necessary, it is a parallel process, so that the complete digital eco system in Serbia can be even better.

REFERENCE:

1. Program for the development of electronic commerce in the Republic of Serbia for the period 2019-2020
2. Soumitra Dutta and Bruno Lanvin (Editors), *The Network Readiness Index 2020: Accelerating Digital Transformation in a post-COVID Global Economy*, Washington, DC: Portulans Institute, 2020
3. UNCTAD, *COVID-19 and e-commerce: a global review*, Geneva, 2021
4. USAID Economic Development Cooperation Project, "1000 Enterprises" Survey, Belgrade, 2020
5. WEF, *Critical Frontier: Leveraging Technology to Combat COVID-19*, Geneva, 2020.
6. https://nbs.rs/sr_RS/indeks/; National Bank of Serbia
7. <https://apr.gov.rs/home.1435.html>; The Serbian Business Registers Agency
8. <https://pks.rs/>; Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Serbia
9. <https://www.stat.gov.rs/>; Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia
10. <https://www.statista.com/>
11. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database>